

LOGO COLOUR PALETTE

BLUE GRADIENT

FROM
R 0 G 174 B 239
#00aeef

TO
R 82 G 79 B 161
#524fa1

ALTERNATIVE COLOUR PALETTE

PURPLE GRADIENT

FROM
R 236 G 0 B 140
#ec008c

TO
R 82 G 79 B 161
#524fa1

Vivid Purple + Magenta RGB colours /

R 255 G 0 B 255
#ff00ff

R 190 G 45 B 180
#be2db4

R 111 G 23 B 97
#6f1761

R 49 G 137 B 197
#3189c5